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IGF1 expression defines TNBC in women of white race.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We measured total transcription in the TNBC tumor genome in white and black women to identify genes that define tumor gene signature in separate haplotypes. We report here activation of the insulin-like growth factor Igf1 in human TNBC in women of white race. A receptor encoded by the IGFL2 gene, known as IGF-like receptor 2, was enriched in the tumors of white women with TNBC.